

Evaluating YOLOv8 and YOLO11 for Real-time Object detection

Anthony Amankwah¹, Chris Aldrich²

¹Amankwah Consult, Email amankwah@ieee.org

²Curtin University E-mail chris.aldrich@curtin.edu.au

Author Correspondence: Schwabhauser Str 3,82269 Kaltenberg, Germany Email amankwah@ieee.org

Abstract

Object detection is one of the important and challenging task in industrial machine vision. In this work, we evaluate YOLO8 and YOLO11 which are among the latest version of YOLO (you only look one) which one-stage deep learning detector. We use small datasets of 140 images per class and 20 image per class for racoons and mushrooms respectively. We present the accuracy and precision results of YOLO8 and YOLO11. The results show that the performance of YOLO11 is similar to YOLO8 after 100 epochs. The mean average precision (mAP) using the datasets for YOLOv8 and YOLO11 are 0.919 and 0.916 respectively.

Keywords: YOLOv8, YOLO11, mAP

1. Introduction

Machine vision is a fast developing field which enables machines to interpret and understand visual data [1]. An important aspect of this area is object detection [2], which involves the precise identification and localization of objects within images scenes. In the traditional methods includes The first step consists in inspecting the entire image at multiple positions and scales to generate candidate boxes with the use of methods like sliding window [3]. The second step involves the extraction of the feature like such as Haar-Like features[4] and Histograms of Oriented Gradients [5]. The final step involves the classification which uses algorithms such as Support Vector Machines [6], and Adaboost [7]. The traditional methods are computationally expensive.

Deep learning-based object detection models using convolutional neural networks and transformers have reduced the error detection rate drastically. The emergence of Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) in 2012, particularly with AlexNet [8] on the ImageNet dataset, marked a turning point. CNNs automated the learning of spatial hierarchies of features, making deep learning-based approaches far more effective and scalable for object detection. YOLO is a one-stage object detector. Two-stage deep learning object detection [11] divides the detection process into two phases: the first involves the proposal of object candidates through the region of interest, and the second phase conducts the object identification of the proposed region of interest candidates. The two-stage approach is considered to result in more accurate detection than the one-stage approach. However, due to the pre-processing in the first stage of the two-stage technique, this approach is also considered slower than the latter approach. Hence, a one-stage method is more convenient for use in machine vision systems. YOLOv8 [9] uses a combination of convolutional neural networks (CNNs) and vision transformer (ViT) blocks to improve feature extraction, while optimizing speed for real-time applications. YOLO11 [10] build upon YOLOv8 by introducing new advance features. In this paper, we evaluate the performance of YOLOv8 and YOLO11 by using mean average precision (mAP) of objects predicted.

2. Architectures of YOLOv8 and YOLO11

2.1 YOLOv8

The architecture of the backbone of YOLOv8 is shown in Figure 1.

(a) Backbone:

It is the convolutional neural network (CNN) responsible for extracting features from the input image. YOLOv8 uses a custom CSPDarknet53 backbone, which employs cross-stage partial connections to improve information flow between layers and boost accuracy.

(b) Neck:

The neck is the feature extractor, combines feature maps from different stages of the backbone to capture information at various scales. This part is in charge of fusing the features extracted by the backbone. It uses a PANet (Path Aggregation Network) to combine features at different scales.

(c) Head:

The head module is responsible for making predictions. YOLOv8 employs multiple detection modules that predict bounding boxes coordinates, object confidence scores, and class probabilities for each grid cell in the feature map. These predictions are then aggregated to obtain the final detections

Figure 1: Architecture diagram of YOLOv8 algorithm: image source: <https://yolov8.org/what-is-yolov8/>).

Figure 2. YOLOv11 network structure diagram

2.2 YOLO11 Architecture

The YOLO11 architecture is an enhancement of the YOLOv8 architecture (Figure.2).

(a) Backbone:

An improvement in YOLO11 is the introduction of the C3k2 block which replaces the C2f block used in previous versions [13]. The C3k2 block is a more computationally efficient implementation of the Cross Stage Partial (CSP) Bottleneck. It employs two smaller convolutions instead of one large convolution as in YOLOv8. YOLO11 retains the Spatial Pyramid Pooling (SPPF) block but introduces a new Cross Stage Partial with Spatial Attention (C2PSA) block after it. This enhances spatial attention in feature maps.

(b) Neck

YOLO11 replace the C2f block in the neck with the C3k2 block. The C3k2 block is faster and more efficient, enhancing the overall performance of the feature aggregation process resulting in enhanced speed and performance [13]. Spatial attention is introduced through the C2PSA module. This attention mechanism enables the model to concentrate on key regions within the image, potentially leading to more accurate detection, especially for smaller or partially occluded objects. The inclusion of C2PSA differentiates YOLO11 apart from its predecessor, YOLOv8, which lacks this specific attention mechanism [13]

(c) Head

The head of YOLOv11 includes several CBS (Convolution-Batch Norm- Silu) [14] layers after the C3k2 blocks. These layers further process the feature maps by extracting relevant features for accurate object detection and normalizing the data flow through batch normalization

3. Experiment and Results

3.1 Datasets and Training

Two small datasets used to train and test the models in this project was obtained from the roboflow website (/universe.roboflow.com/).The first dataset contains 196 images of raccoons and 213 bounding boxes (some images have two raccoons). This is a single class problem, and images vary in dimensions. The images dimensions are 416 x 416 pixels. The second dataset contains images of popular North American mushrooms, Chicken of the Woods (CoW) and Chanterelle, differentiating between the two species. The dataset consists of 51 images.

The image dimensions are 416 x 416 pixels. The Google Colab platform was used for the training. We trained for 100 epoches with a batch size of 64.

3.2 The Metrics for Evaluation

Mean Average Precision (mAP) is final measure used for evaluating YOLO11 and Yolov8 models as it provides a single metric encapsulating precision and recall across multiple classes. Intersection over Union (IoU) measures the overlap between the predicted and ground truth bounding boxes. mAP@0.50 measures precision at an IoU threshold of 0.50, focusing on the model's ability to detect objects correctly. Whiles mAP@0.50:0.95 averages precision across a range of IoU threshold.

Precision (P) is the accuracy of positive predictions:

$$P = \frac{TP}{TP+FP} \quad (1)$$

Where TP is outcomes that are correctly predicted as positives. False Positives (FP) is outcomes inaccurately predicted as positives.

Recall (R) measures the proportion of actual positive cases correctly identified by the model.

$$R = \frac{TP}{TP+FN} \tag{2}$$

where False Negatives (FN) is outcomes inaccurately predicted as negatives.

Average precision (AP) summarizes a precision-recall (PR) curve into a single value representing the average of all precisions. The general definition the AP is finding the area under the precision-recall curve above. mAP is the average of AP.

3.2 Results

The training loss and validation loss curves for the datasets are similar for YOLOv8 and YOLO11. The object detection of racoons illustrated in Figure 5 show that both YOLOv8 and YOLO11 models detected the racoons very well. Both models reached the highest overall precision in terms of mAP@50 of 1 (100%) as shown in Figure 3 and Figure 4. The mAP@50:95 for the YOLO11 and YOLOv8 are 0.688 and 0.697 respectively. Thus the mAP for YOLO 11 and YOLOv8 are 0.844 and 0.849 respectively. Figure 8 shows the object detection of mushrooms in an image using YOLOv8 and YOLO11. Both models reached the highest overall precision in terms of mAP@50 of 1 (100%) This is shown in Figure 6 and Figure 7. . The mAP@50:95 for the YOLO11 and YOLOv8 are 0.986 and 0.976 respectively. Thus the mAP for YOLO 11 and YOLOv8 are 0.993 and 0.988 respectively. This high score is interesting since only 20 image per class was used for training.

Figure 3 Training results of Racoon dataset using YOLOv8 model after 100 epochs

Figure 4 Training results of Racoon dataset using YOLOv11 model after 100 epochs

Figure 5 (a) prediction of racoon using YOLOv8 (b) prediction of racoon using YOLO 11

Figure 6 Training results of mushroom dataset using YOLOv8 model after 100 epochs

4. Conclusions

In this paper, we test the performance of YOLOv8 and YOLO11 models on two small datasets. The small datasets of 140 images per class and 20 images per class for racoons and mushrooms respectively. We show the accuracy and precision results of YOLO8 and YOLO11. The results show that the performance of YOLO11 is similar to YOLO8 after 100 epochs. The mean average precision mAP using the datasets for YOLOv8 and YOLO11 are 0.919 and 0.916 respectively. In future, we will test the algorithm on more datasets.

References

- 1) Milan Sonka, Vaclav Hlavac, and Roger Boyle. Image processing, analysis and machine vision. Springer, 2013.
- 2) Zhengxia Zou, Keyan Chen, Zhenwei Shi, Yuhong Guo, and Jieping Ye. Object detection in 20 years: A survey. *Proceedings of the IEEE*, 111(3):257–276, 2023
- 3) H. Schneiderman, T. Kanade, Object Detection Using the Statistics of Parts, *International Journal of Computer Vision*
- 4) R. Lienhart, J. Maydt, An extended set of Haar-like features for rapid object detection, in: *Proceedings. International Conference on Image Processing, IEEE, Rochester, NY, USA, 2002*: p. I-900–I-903 <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICIP.2002.1038171>
- 5) N. Dalal, B. Triggs, Histograms of Oriented Gradients for Human Detection, in: *2005 IEEE Computer Society Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR '05)*, IEEE, San Diego, CA, USA, 2005: pp. 886–893. <https://doi.org/10.1109/CVPR.2005.177>
- 6) C. Cortes, V. Vapnik, Support-vector networks, *Mach Learn.* 20 (1995) 273–297. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00994018>.
- 7) Y. Freund, R.E. Schapire, A Decision-Theoretic Generalization of On-Line Learning and an Application to Boosting, *Journal of Computer and System Sciences.* 55 (1997) 119–139. <https://doi.org/10.1006/jcss.1997.1504>
- 8) A. Krizhevsky, I. Sutskever, G.E. Hinton, ImageNet Classification with Deep Convolutional Neural Networks, in: F. Pereira, C.J.C. Burges, L. Bottou, K.Q. Weinberger (Eds.), *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems 25*, Curran Associates, Inc., 2012: pp. 1097–1105. <http://papers.nips.cc/paper/4824-imagenet-classification-with-deep-convolutional-neural-networks.pdf> (accessed October 22, 2019).
- 9) Jocher, G., Chaurasia, A., & Qiu, J. (2023). Ultralytics YOLOv8. Retrieved from <https://github.com/ultralytics/ultralytics>
- 10) Ultralytics Abirami Vina. Ultralytics yolo11 has arrived: Redefine what's possible in ai, 2024. Accessed: 2024-10-21
- 11) Ansari, M.F.; Lodi, K.A. A survey of recent trends in two-stage object detection methods. In *Proceedings of the Renewable Power for Sustainable Growth: Proceedings of International Conference on Renewal Power (ICRP 2020)*, Rajouri, India, 17–18 April 2020
- 12) Wang, Chien-Yao. "CSPNet: A new backbone that can enhance learning capability of CNN." *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF conference on computer vision and pattern recognition workshops*. 2020.

- 13) Satya Mallick. Yolo - learnopencv. <https://learnopencv.com/yolo11/>, 2024. Accessed: 2024-12-18
- 14) Jingwen Feng, Qiaofeng An, Jiahao Zhang, Shuxun Zhou, Guangwei Du, and Kai Yang. Application of yolov7-tiny in the detection of steel surface defects. In 2024 5th International Seminar on Artificial Intelligence, Networking and Information Technology (AINIT), pages 2241–2245. IEEE, 2024

A Brief Author Biography

Anthony Amankwah -received a B.Sc. degree in metallurgical engineering from the Kwame Nkrumah University of Science and Technology, Kumasi, Ghana in 1996 and B.Sc. and M.Sc. degrees in electrical engineering and computer science respectively from the University of Duisburg-Essen, Duisburg, Germany in 2003. He received a Ph.D. degree in electrical and computer science from the University of Siegen, Siegen, Germany.

Chris Aldrich - is a Fellow of the South African Academic of Engineering and Professor and Head of the Department of Process Engineering at the University of Stellenbosch in South Africa. His research interests include machine learning, data mining and advanced process modeling and control systems in the chemical and mineral processing industries.